

The Bubonic Plague in Bombay and Pune (1896-1897)

Gargi Mukherjee

Visva-Bharati, Shantiniketan, West Bengal

The Bombay plague epidemic was a bubonic plague that struck the city of Bombay in the late nineteenth century. The plague killed thousands, and many fled the city leading to a drastic fall in the population of the city. In September 1896 the first case of bubonic plague was detected in Mandvi, Bombay, by Acacio Gabriel Viegas. It spread rapidly to other parts of the city, and the death toll was estimated at 1,900 people per week through the rest of the year. Many people fled from Bombay at this time, and in the census of 1901, the population had actually fallen to 780,000. Viegas correctly diagnosed the disease as bubonic plague and tended to patients at great personal risk

From Bombay, it spread quickly to Bengal, Punjab, the United Provinces, and later even to Burma. However, its impact was most severe in Western and Northern India, while southern and eastern India escaped with relatively fewer deaths. By 1901, 4 lakh Indians were reported dead, and by 1905, the toll was 10 lakh!

Epidemic Disease Act of 1897

As the situation spun out of control, the British hastily drafted the Epidemic Disease Act of 1897 and began to enforce it in India. The Act gave the local authorities the power to do virtually anything they needed to salvage the situation, without

109

110

any legal ramifications. At the time, the Assistant Commissioner of Pune, W C Rand, was tasked with implementing the Act. Initially, Rand made a genuine effort to provide relief by setting up quarantine camps and hospitals, while also disinfecting the plague-affected areas.

“Two kinds of the disease, and both deadly – natives dying by hundreds of hunger – Overseers stealing the supplies.” - A Presbyterian missionary

However, as the situation worsened, Rand adopted brutal measures, which stripped Indians of their dignity. Rand and his men, who included young doctors backed by the army and police, would publicly strip men, women and children in order to inspect sensitive body parts like their groins and armpits for signs of the bubonic plague. Infected individuals would be forcibly quarantined or shifted to hospitals. Often buildings, food, clothes and other properties of the affected individuals were ruthlessly burnt and destroyed, without their permission, during the process of disinfection.

The New York Times reporting the plague in June 1897 quoted a Presbyterian priest who had said, “Two kinds of the disease, and both deadly—natives dying by hundreds of hunger —Overseers stealing the supplies” Even though people who were simply suspected of being infected were forcibly taken away to detention centres, measures like these did not help bring the disease under control. Instead, they aggravated its spread, especially among the ones kept in detention centres.

Bombay faced the same situation as did Pune, and according to Cynthia Deshmukh in her 1988 journal article titled *The Bombay Plague* (1896-1897), communities like the Jains, Bhatias and the Baniyas living in chawls in the Mandvi locality added to the woes by refusing to allow the killing of rats due to their religious beliefs. In

111

addition, a majority of citizens in Bombay refused to believe that they were infected and refused to go to hospitals and quarantine camps. Sometimes, their protestations caused large-scale chaos.

A majority of citizens refused to believe that they were infected and refused to go to quarantine camps.

Deshmukh in her paper cites the instance of a Parsi family who had a 13-year-old, infected Hindu boy living with them. The women in the family wielded knives and surrounded the boy so that he would not be taken away. They threatened to commit suicide using the knives if the boy was taken. The boy died the next day in the Parsi household, as neither the police nor the health officer could convince the women. The brutal steps taken by the British administration and the indignities they heaped on the local people led to a build-up of outrage. Add fear to the mix and it created for a very explosive situation. Once the reality of the plague began to sink in, panic gripped the people and thousands began to flee Bombay, taking the epidemic with them.

The Outrage Spills Over

Amid the chaos and din, the British government realised that a foreign ruling entity could not effectively tackle the situation without taking into account the social customs and mores followed by the natives. This led to the rise of a middle-class Indian leadership in the Bombay Presidency, and those with an English education tried to mediate with the British government.

The Plague in Pune

It all started in 1896 when the deadly plague reached Pune. It had initially affected the coastal cities with ports, but owing to its proximity to Mumbai, Pune too had been affected by it. By

112

the beginning of January 1897, it had become nothing short of an epidemic.

In just a month, about 0.6% of Pune's population of 1,70,000 had succumbed to the disease. Nearly half of the population had run away from the city. That means about a lakh of people perished in Pune alone!

Rand had initially provided some relief—establishing a hospital, quarantine camps, in addition to disinfecting affected areas. However, these initiatives soon paved the way for more brutal steps that would rip the dignity of the affected families, and ignite the fire of anger among the minds like the Chapekar brothers, who tragically killed two British officers.

Conclusion

Almost 125 years ago when Mumbai and Pune experienced the terrible consequences of bubonic plague killing thousands of people, it may be remembered that it led to further exploitation of the poor. Overseers were stealing the supplies meant for the hungry. It also led to violence and killing of British officers. It is really sad that even during the time of major disaster the human hatred can still win over our hearts!

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113

114